

Appendix B: Additional Figures

In Figures B.1, B.2 and B.3 we present the continuum subtractions for the $2\ \mu\text{m}$ region, the $4\ \mu\text{m}$ region and the $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ stretching mode at $4.27\ \mu\text{m}$.

Appendix B.1: Continuum subtractions

Fig. B.1. Continuum subtraction for the ^{12}CO overtone mode (left) and $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ combination mode (right). The purple line illustrates the local continuum drawn over each band.

Fig. B.2. Continuum subtraction for the $^{13}\text{CO}_2$, ^{12}CO and ^{13}CO stretching modes in the $4\ \mu\text{m}$ region for B1a-S (strong CO gas lines) and L1527 (weak CO gas lines). The purple line illustrates the local continuum placed over this region.

Fig. B.3. Continuum subtraction for the $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ $4.27\ \mu\text{m}$ stretching mode. The purple line illustrates the local continuum placed over the band.

Appendix B.2: Band Overview

Appendix B.2.1: NIRSpect 4 μm region

In Figures B.4, B.5, B.6, B.7, B.8 B.9, B.10 and B.11 we present an overview of the CO_2 and CO ice features in the 4 μm and 15 μm region.

Fig. B.4. Overview of the $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ (left), ^{12}CO (middle) and ^{13}CO (right) stretching modes in the 4 μm region.

Fig. B.5. Overview of the $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ (left), ^{12}CO (middle) and ^{13}CO (right) stretching modes in the $4\ \mu\text{m}$ region.

Fig. B.6. Overview of the $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ (left), ^{12}CO (middle) and ^{13}CO (right) stretching modes in the $4\ \mu\text{m}$ region.

Fig. B.7. A zoom in of the $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ absorption features that suffer from gaseous CO line contamination. The Gaussian curves (pink) fitted to the bands illustrate the bounds used to determine the integrated optical depths.

Fig. B.8. A zoom in of the ^{13}CO absorption features. The Gaussian curves (pink) fitted to the bands illustrate the bounds used to determine the integrated optical depths.

Appendix B.2.2: MIRI 15 μm region

Fig. B.9. Continuum and silicate subtraction for the of the $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ bending mode in the 15 μm region. The left panel shows the fitting of the continuum (purple line). The middle panel shows the two Gaussian profiles (red and pink lines) and the combined final fit (orange line) that simulates the silicate absorption feature at 18 μm . For EDJ183-a and EDJ183-b an additional Gaussian profile (green line) was fitted to simulate the silicate feature in emission. The third panel shows the resulting spectra in optical depth scale.

Fig. B.10. Continuum and silicate subtraction for the of the $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ bending mode in the $15\ \mu\text{m}$ region. The left panel shows the fitting of the continuum (purple line). The middle panel shows the two Gaussian profiles (red and pink lines) and the combined final fit (orange line) that simulates the silicate absorption feature at $18\ \mu\text{m}$. For EDJ183-a and EDJ183-b an additional Gaussian profile (green line) was fitted to simulate the silicate feature in emission. The third panel shows the resulting spectra in optical depth scale.

Fig. B.11. Continuum and silicate subtraction for the of the $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ bending mode in the $15\ \mu\text{m}$ region. The left panel shows the fitting of the continuum (purple line). The middle panel shows the two Gaussian profiles (red and pink lines) and the combined final fit (orange line) that simulates the silicate absorption feature at $18\ \mu\text{m}$. For EDJ183-a and EDJ183-b an additional Gaussian profile (green line) was fitted to simulate the silicate feature in emission. The third panel shows the resulting spectra in optical depth scale.

Appendix B.3: Additional features

Figure B.12 shows the 2.70 μm and 2.77 μm combination modes of CO_2 with the laboratory spectrum of pure CO_2 fitted to the data. Figure B.13 shows the silicate bands in emission in the source EDJ183-a. In Figure B.14 we show the $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ 4.27 μm band of Per-emb35 and finally in Figure B.15 we show the photospheric model fittings for TMC1-E.

Fig. B.12. Laboratory fittings of the 2.70 and 2.77 combination modes. The spectrum of pure CO_2 at 80 K (Ehrenfreund et al. 1997) is plotted over the two absorption feature in pink.

Fig. B.13. MIRI spectrum of EDJ183-a showing the 9 and 18 μm silicate features in emission. The 18 μm silicate bending mode is likely responsible for the distortion of the long-wavelength wing of the CO_2 absorption band at 15.2 μm .

Fig. B.14. The 4.27 μm band of Per-emb35. Plotted over the band is the $\text{CO}_2:\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 1:10 spectrum at 10 K (Ehrenfreund et al. 1999).

Fig. B.15. Photospheric model fittings for TMC1-E using the Starfish MCMC exploration (Le Gouellec et al. 2024, Le Gouellec in prep.). Panel A shows the 'red-shifted' 2.35 μm absorption feature with the spectrum of pure CO ice plotted over the feature (pink). Panel B shows the full 1.9 - 2.45 μm spectrum (red) with the best fit model plotted over the data (black). The grey dot-dashed line shows the disk component of the model while the grey solid line shows the photosphere component of the model. In panel C we show the residuals and the diagonal of the covariance matrix as σ contours. Finally, in panel D we show the relative errors (residuals to data flux ratio).

Appendix C: Source coordinates

In Table C.1 we present the coordinates of the apertures used to extract the spectra.

Table C.1. Coordinates of extracted spectra.

Source	RA NIRSpec	Dec NIRSpec	RA MIRI	Dec MIRI
B1-a-N	3:33:16.693	31:07:55.274	3:33:16.692	31:07:55.286
B1-a-S	3:33:16.677	31:07:54.969	3:33:16.681	31:07:54.897
B1-b	3:33:20.334	31:07:21.634	3:33:20.354	31:07:21.353
B1-c	3:33:17.893	31:09:31.900	3:33:17.893	31:09:31.847
L1547	4:39:53.875	26:03:09.5940	4:39:53.836	26:03:10.153
Per-emb22	3:25:22.351	30:45:13.186	3:25:22.349	30:45:13.111
Per-emb27	3:28:55.575	31:14:36.900	3:28:55.573	31:14:36.764
Per-emb33	3:25:36.308	30:45:15.018	3:25:36.304	30:45:14.958
Per35	3:28:37.093	31:13:30.837	3:28:37.100	31:13:30.657
Per55-a	3:44:43.292	32:01:31.428	3:44:43.293	32:01:31.187
Per55-b	3:44:43.324	32:01:31.819	3:44:43.325	32:01:31.592
EDJ183-a	3:28:59.301	31:15:48.473	3:28:59.301	31:15:48.314
EDJ183-b	3:28:59.379	31:15:48.465	3:28:59.381	31:15:48.314
Ser-S68N-N	18:29:48.134	1:16:44.574	18:29:48.133	1:16:44.489
Ser-SMM3	18:29:59.307	1:14:00.680	18:29:59.317	1:14:00.732
TMC1-E	4:41:12.730	25:46:34.524	4:41:12.735	25:46:34.715
TMC1-W	4:41:12.684	25:46:34.518	4:41:12.686	25:46:34.730